

MAQSUD SHAYKHZODA AND UZBEK POETRY
OF THE 20TH CENTURY
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Annotation: the article glorifies the immortal creative activity of Maqsd Shaykhhzoda, who created her poetry using a palette of colors, methods of using words and skillful metaphors.

Keywords: kinship, ohangrabo, old language, Turkic language, related languages, Uzbek, Turkmen, Azerbaijani, uncle.

Maqsd Shaykhzoda is the beloved child of two great peoples, with a sharp pencil, a blessed creator in various genres of literature, a poet playwright, scientist, translator and a wonderful teacher.

Maksud Shaikhzo was born in makoni Azerbaijan, the fountain of creativity is one of the poet who opened their eyes in Uzbekistan and have a place in Uzbek literature. This happiness also has its place in the poet's lines. His memoirs, Maqsd Shaykhzoda recalls that the poetry entered his life before he recognized the alphabet, and at the age of five he invented of 8-10 verses about a diamond with a wolf and a squirrel. Maqsd Shaykhzoda is a prolific creator, his ruboists, ballads, epic works have become lost in the readers' heart. As we read the poems of the poet, we come to the realization that the melody, the deep meaning, the proximity of words to the vernacular, the simplicity of which is a place for the hearts of readers. As we read Maqsd Shaikhzoda's "poets of kinship", we can judge from such royal lines.

“Qardoshlik-ko‘ngillararo ko‘prikdir,
Ko‘zlarning soqchisi nozik kiprikdir
Tillar har turli-yu, tilmoch kerakmas,
Har tilda besh burchak yulduz-tabrikdur”.

Look at the play of fate, the author does not see this work published

he turned a blind eye from the universe. The full text of "Jaloliddin Manguberdi" was first published in Baku, it was printed and released in Azerbaijani in the two-volume edition of Shaykhzoda. It was not until 1988 that Jaloliddin Manguberdi was first published in full print by an Uzbek-language writer in his book "The Immortal World". The history of the Shaykhzoda of our people, including the fate of Jalaliddin Manguberdi and the first to approach his struggle with justice, to defend the truth President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, signed by Islam Karimov. The Cabinet's 24 September 1998 "Jaloliddin Manguberdi the decision" on the celebration of the 800th anniversary of the birth " also confirms once again.

Once again, the glory of shaikhzoda as a writer and the sharpness of the mind of creativity proved. Another great addition of Maqsud Shaykhzoda to Uzbek literature the contribution is the tragedy "Mirzo Ulugbek". The tragedy was written in 1964, the same year it was the work was put on the stage of the Hamza Theater, on the basis of which a feature film was later created. Maqsud Shaykhzoda was the owner of high knowledge. In particular, he described Uzbek classical literature as he knew deeply. Collection "general poet" published in Tashkent in 1941, Organization of scientific articles on the work of the literary scientist Shaykhzoda Navoi found. This in-depth scientific study of Navoi poetry is always in navoiology a separate seat remains. Shaikhzoda noted Navoi's skill, his artistry was a keen explorer who pioneered the study. Candidate of philological Sciences, associate professor Maqsud Shaykhzoda Tashkent State University (now Uzbekistan national University, Tashkent State Pedagogical Institute (now Tashkent State Pedagogical University) in the history of Uzbek literature for many years lectures, special courses the most valuable lessons on the history of Uzbek literature.

Maqsud Shaykhzoda was one of the poet who praised friendship. In memory of his contemporary and maslakite Ghafur Ghulam, we read the lines in the poem "letter to Ghafur";

"G'afur G'ulom va o'lim-qovushmagan gap,

Misoli qish va rayhon, dasht buloqlar
Gʻafur Gʻulom va sukut-ikki yov lashkar,
Nuqul urishagotgan dushman taraflar”.

From the point of view of skill, we read the poetic lines of the poet, in the lines the tone rises to its high point. The entire work of Maqsud Shaykhzoda is full of a deep political publicistic spirit. His poetic, dramatic works are in harmony with the times, no matter what theme they are devoted to. That is why it is not accidental that a creator of this type serves directly in the genre of journalism. His publicistic articles and speeches, which have an excellent artistic genre, are a bright badge from the content and colorfulness of this talented poet creativity. The talented poet was also a skilled translator. He served greatly in translating the works of classical poets of world literature into Uzbek. In particular, Shakespeare's "Hamlet" and "Romeo and Juliet" were staged on the stage of Uzbek drama theaters in the translation of the Shaykhzoda. There is also a Shaykhzoda within the generation of poets who first presented the poems of Pushkin, Lermontov, Byron to the Uzbek reader. The growth of the poet's skill was also due to the fact that he studied in great love the works of the classics of world literature, masterfully mastering their rich artistic experience. He had also thoroughly studied his fatherland literature - the heritage of Oriental poetry-with an excellent knowledge of Western European and Russian literature.”

Maqsud Shaykhzoda was deeply interested in the issues of the history of Eastern literature. In Eastern literature, the existing works were sufficiently restrained by their genre features, issues of contribution. Maqsud Shaykhzoda, who learned a lot from the most progressive and progressive non-speakers of Uzbek classical literature, seems to have perfected artistic skill and literary genre. He studied such high human qualities as hard work in classical poetry, devotion to science, courage and friendship with unique artistic methods, lyrical genres such as spiritual and rubory, and began to successfully apply them in the process of his creative work. Maqsud also worked with Blessing on the enrichment of lyrical types and genres in Shaykhzoda's poetry.

In conclusion, Maqsd Shaykhzoda is one of the poets who have reached the peak of the poetry of the two peoples. The Uzbek people are always proud that there is such a creative person. We think that later generations will also receive miriqib ifor from flowers in the flower of the poetry of Maqsd Shaykhzoda.

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